

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPOSITE SUBMARINE RADOME

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ABSTRACT

A pressure vessel was developed which would protect a radar unit, yet allow it to operate in the same fashion as a submarine periscope. This radome is transparent to radar signals and will withstand an extremely hostile environment while protecting very delicate equipment.

The radomes were filament wound using Kevlar™, S-2 glass, and graphite in an epoxy matrix. Mounting and reinforcement components are of stainless steel. The development of the structures went through two basic designs.

This paper describes the radome development and illustrates the problems and their solutions in taking a complex composite concept through to a successful working piece of hardware.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The objective of the programs described herein was to design, develop, proof-test, and produce radomes which would protect radar units mounted on the masts of submarines. The problems which had to be solved by the design/manufacturing team were:

1. Survival in an extremely hostile environment while completely protecting delicate electronics,
2. Exhibit minimal distortion of radar signals,
3. Disassembly/Assembly capability in the field,
4. Provide minimal radar cross-section, and
5. Be reproducible at a reasonable cost.

Two different designs were completed, tested, and proven to be totally successful. The purpose of this paper is to document the design and manufacturing history of these developments, and hopefully provide insight to others undertaking similar projects. As such, no details providing information as to the technical capabilities of the submarine or the radar units will be given; all relevant measurements are non-dimensionalized.

The work described herein took place over a five-year period. All fabrication was done by Advanced Composite Products and Technology, Inc., and all design calculations were

accomplished by H. D. Neubert and Associates. To this author's knowledge, these units are still operational and fleet deployed.

2.0 DESIGN CONSIDERATION

2.1 Design Requirements – The first design had to withstand external pressure P , and the second $1.5 P$. Both units were required to undergo cyclic testing to 90% of design pressure ($0.9 P$ and $1.35 P$ respectively) prior to delivery to customer. Since attenuation of a radar signal is a direct function of the radome wall thickness, the walls were minimal and the design pressures P and $1.5 P$ were the design collapse (failure predicted) pressure. The designs also included allowances and calculations for the radomes to withstand:

- wave slap: 5 tons/m²
- wind resistance: 100 km /hr
- water resistance at submerged running speeds
- nuclear blast
- functional temperatures: -80°F to +160°F.

2.2 Design Approach – The following is a description of the initial analysis performed on the second, more complex radome. Due to the complex structural configurations and unusual design requirements, a NASTRAN cyclic symmetry finite element analysis was initiated to provide necessary accuracy. Intermediate results from the NASTRAN analysis indicated regions of the radomes having high stresses and excessive deformations.

The interior design was revised three times, whereby changes in dome and cylinder thickness were implemented, and base ring as well as composite structure at the joint overlap were modified. All design work and iterations were continuously coordinated with the planned fabrication effort.

The procedures used to obtain the resulting designs are summarized below:

1. Computer program "CONTUR.FOR" was run to establish mandrel coordinates, mean line coordinates of the filament wound dome (data required in NASTRAN), dome thickness variation from the dome/cylinder junction to the pole piece, and material angular orientation changes from the dome/cylinder junction to the pole piece.
2. The upper dome was divided into seven (7) sections, while the lower dome was divided into eight (8) sections. Each of these elements has a unique thickness and material orientation. Program elements have a unique thickness and material orientation. Program SQ5N.FOR¹ was run to generate the equivalent elastic properties, thermal properties, and maximum strength allowable for each element using individual ply input properties. Results of the SQ5N.FOR program are used to create the NASTRAN MAT2 and PSHELL input cards which define the structure's elastic behavior.
3. Since the structure is axisymmetric, the cyclic symmetry option (Solution 47) of the MSC/NASTRAN finite element computer program was utilized. With this procedure, the entire structural behavior of the radome was simulated by a 15° pie segment. During program execution, the rotational symmetry boundary conditions were generated. Therefore, only a segment of the finite element model was necessary for input. Program DOME.FOR was written to generate grid points and shell elements of the model, typically a tedious job and prone to error when attempted by hand. The card images were sent via

¹ SQ5N is a point stress analysis program for multi-layered orthotropic materials, copyright 1983 by H. D. Neubert and Associates, Inc., Anaheim, CA.

modem to the CDC Cybernet center where physical cards were prepared (cards were used primarily to conserve computer costs, but at the expense of a lengthened schedule).

4. At the completion of the design iteration, the maximum loads from the NASTRAN analysis (membrane forces and bending moments) for each set of elements were input into SQ5N.FOR, along with the worst case operating temperature, and margins of safety on a ply-by-ply basis were computed.

5. Additional analysis was performed by classical/empirical methods to verify that the remaining requirements would be met.

3.0 MATERIALS OF CONSTRUCTION

During the course of the development program the following materials were used:

- Naval bronze – Mounting rings
- Stainless steel – Mounting rings and cut-out reinforcement
- S-2 glass – Compression components of Shell
- Kevlar 49™ – Axial stiffness components of Shell
- Graphite fiber – Hoop stiffness component of Shell
- Polyester – Matrix system first design
- Epoxy – Matrix system second design and all bond joints and overlays.

The final design used stainless steel, S-2 glass, Kevlar, Graphite and epoxy. Kevlar and S-2 glass were the only reinforcements given serious consideration for the window regions of the radome; they were chosen for their mechanical properties and their ability to transmit radar signals without catastrophic attenuation. Graphite was used to alleviate a stiffness mismatch problem between the base mounting plate and the composite radome body. Kevlar is much stiffer (higher modulus) than the S-2 glass, but has poor compressive strength. Therefore, the helical (more axial) orientation used Kevlar, while S-2 glass was used to provide hoop winding (compressive strength). Epoxy provided the better matrix required for the more demanding second design.

4.0 FIRST DESIGN

4.1 Design and Fabrication – The first radome, shown in Figure 1, was a simple domed cylinder design. The design calculations were similar to those described previously in Section 2.0. The mounting base ring was machined from a naval bronze casting and the body was filament wound using S-2 glass (hoop and helical windings) and polyester resin. The top of the dome (penetration caused by the winding mandrel) was sealed by bonding in a cap machined from a G10 glass plate and overlaying it with 7781 glass cloth. The base of the radome was open and, when in use, was sealed by double "O" rings in the O.D. of the base plate and mating with the I.D. of the base ring.

4.2 Testing and First Developmental Problems – All of the "first design" radomes were tested by the Civil Engineering Laboratory of the California State University at Long Beach, CA. After cyclic testing of the first unit, water was found inside the radome. Since the source of the leak was not immediately obvious, the test was re-run with die penetrant added to the pressure chamber. Subsequent evaluations proved that the water had entered not through the composite, as feared, but through the porous 1" thick naval bronze base ring. This problem was solved by replacing the bronze base ring with one machined from 4" thick stainless steel sheet stock.

5.0 SECOND DESIGN

5.1 Design Considerations – The second generation radome was required to function at a 50%

FIGURE 1: SINGLE DOME RADOMES

greater pressure (1.5 P) than the first design. The wall thickness, t , of the first design was already at the maximum allowed by the electronics of the radar. Greater wall thickness would have increased the attenuation of the radar signal beyond allowable levels. This design enigma was solved through application of two factors:

- 1) The radome housed units operating at two different frequencies. The higher frequency unit was the most severely affected by wall attenuation. This unit was also the smallest.
- 2) The required wall thickness of a cylindrical pressure vessel decreases with decreasing diameter.

The theoretical solution thus became obvious: build a radome with one section to house the lower frequency unit and a smaller diameter to house the smaller unit. Therefore, a two-tiered unit was designed. Completed two-tier radomes are shown in Figure 2.

This seemingly simple solution created a second basic design problem: opening the top of the large dome was analogous to removing the keystone from a bridge. The design must now be capable of carrying the load around the hole in the dome. The solution seemed obvious. Simply reinforce the base of the top dome, below its radar window, with bands of graphite fiber wound into the wall. The solution was ideal, since the top dome, as shown in the cross sectional sketch, Figure 3, would require a greater wall thickness at its base. This increased thickness would provide the area needed for a secure bond between the two domes.

As a final design complication, calculations showed that after numerous pressure cycles the stiffness discrepancy between the thick-walled stainless mounting ring and the glass/Kevlar wall could result in damage to the wall.

To alleviate this problem, a taper, to nearly a knife-edge, was designed into the top of the mounting ring. Further analysis showed that at maximum submergence this "knife-edge" would experience permanent deformation. Again, the solution was obvious: stiffen the base of the radome wall, below the radar window, by adding several layers of graphite.

FIGURE 2: TWO-TIER RADOMES

FIGURE 3: CROSS-SECTION, TWO-TIER RADOMES

The design was then completed by using a similar top-dome closure (as per first design) and by also overlaying the exterior of the dome-to-dome joint with 7781 glass cloth to provide adequate rigidity against wave slap and submerged running loads.

5.2 Fabrication – Each of the two domes was filament wound on a different mandrel. In order to minimize the probability of "window" contamination, winding of the graphite reinforcement on the large dome was accomplished in two steps: 1) first directly onto the mandrel, on the ID of the

radome, and then 2) midway through the wall. The graphite in the upper dome was all placed in the center of the wall.

After curing, the domes and dome caps were match machined. The two composite cylinder/dome units were bonded together, the base ring and the dome cap were bonded in place, and the dome cap and the dome joint were reinforced. The unit was painted and pressure tested at the Navy Engineering Station, Port Hueneme, CA.

5.3 Testing, Failure, and Failure Analysis – This first unit failed at approximately .45 P (.3 of 1.5 P). Figure 4 shows the after test remnants of the top dome.

FIGURE 4: TOP DOME, POST-TEST

Careful examination of this part and the design calculations identified the cause of the failure. Completion of the radome required providing eight 1/8" diameter holes (drilled, tapped and fitted with helicoils) for mounting the radar unit to the upper dome. These holes fell within the graphite stiffening rings in the upper dome. Bolts were not placed in these holes prior to testing and the effect of the presence of the holes in the stiffening ring was not accounted for in the design calculations. As the exterior pressure increased, the exterior wall and the remaining graphite crushed into those eight holes. The resultant reduced integrity of the base allowed the top dome to be almost explosively injected downward into the structure and the walls of the lower cylinder crushed.

Recognizing this flaw and not being able to assure that the mounting holes would always be completely filled, the dome hole reinforcement and mounting accommodations were completely redesigned. The new design incorporated two pin-connected stainless steel rings. This modification is illustrated in Figure 5. Figure 6 shows all components of the final two-tier design.

The next four units passed testing flawlessly. After the sixth test (unit 7), which also apparently experienced no failure, inspection of the inside of the radome revealed minor delamination within the inside graphite stiffening ring of the lower, larger cylinder. Detailed ply-by-ply review of the design calculations showed:

FIGURE 5: FINAL JOINT DESIGN

- 1) A positive margin of safety still remained even if most of this interior layer was removed, and
- 2) The delamination experienced was predictable and resulted from a snap-through of the graphite inner bands when the deformation stress exceeded the local inter-laminar strength.

This problem was eliminated simply by moving the graphite layers outward in the wall structure.

FIGURE 6: COMPONENTS, FINAL DESIGN

This development program is an excellent illustration of the problems which, if possible, should be anticipated in designing and fabricating truly composite hardware; hardware which utilizes the correct materials to meet the specific design need. It was also demonstrative of the close cooperation required between design and fabrication efforts in successfully developing composite structures.